

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH
AND MODELLING

D2.5 User guide

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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the findings of the COVINFORM risk assessment dashboard usability testing sequence, which entailed the following activities:

- Workshop 1 (May 2021): online requirements elicitation workshop with public health practitioners within the consortium, including discussion of mock-ups
- Workshop 2 (October 2022): in-person cognitive walkthrough of the dashboard with the full consortium (focus on “Risk Assessment”, “Geospatial Plots”, “Indicator Comparisons”, and “COVID-19 Trends” tabs)
- Workshop 3 (July 2023): online cognitive walkthrough of the dashboard with selected consortium partners (focus on “Case Studies” tab)
- Individual end-user tests (September and October 2023): concurrent think-aloud tests of the full dashboard conducted with N=12 external end-users

The workshops, conducted with project partners, found a number of minor issues but generally suggested good usability. The individual usability tests, conducted with external end-users, identified several more basic challenges. This differential was expected based on the difference in contextual knowledge between the internal workshop participants and the external end-users. The end-user feedback will prove critical in the finalisation of the dashboard, as well as in planning its future exploitation.

A note on the deliverable name: in the Description of Action, the deliverable is titled “User Guide” albeit the description indicating that it should contain results of the usability testing, not a user-facing description of functions and how to use them. These are available in **information boxes** on the site itself, and a walkthrough video is available in D2.9, “Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers”.

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Tables

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
CTA	Concurrent think-aloud
CWW	Cognitive walkthrough for the web
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

1 Introduction

Usability is defined in *ISO 9241-11:2018 Ergonomics of human-system interaction* as “the extent to which a system, product or service can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use” (2018). It is generally not treated as a single construct that can be measured directly, but rather as a composite of several constructs: in the ISO definition, these are:

- **Effectiveness:** “the accuracy and completeness with which users achieve specified goals”
- **Efficiency:** “the resources used in relation to the results achieved” (e.g., time, human effort, cost, and materials)
- **Satisfaction:** “the extent to which the user's physical, cognitive and emotional responses that result from the use of a system, product or service meet the user’s needs and expectations”

Another key dimension is **accessibility**, “the extent to which products, systems, services, environments and facilities can be used by people from a population with the widest range of user needs, characteristics and capabilities to achieve identified goals in identified contexts of use” (ISO 2018). Additional dimensions must be determined on a case-by-case basis depending upon the characteristics of the system being evaluated, the aims of the designers, the needs of the users, and the context of use, among other factors; examples are fun, aesthetics, sociability, and flow (Hornbaek 2006, pg. 80).

Based on the above definitions, *ISO/IEC 25066:2016 Systems and software engineering* suggests the following indicators for measuring the three core usability constructs:

Table 1. Indicators for the dimensions of usability

Effectiveness	Efficiency	Satisfaction
Tasks completed	Task time	Overall satisfaction
Objectives achieved	Time efficiency	Satisfaction with features
Errors in a task	Cost efficiency	Discretionary usage
Tasks with errors	Productive time ratio	Feature utilisation
Task error intensity	Unnecessary actions	Proportion of users complaining
	Fatigue	Proportion of user complaints about a particular feature
		User trust
		User pleasure
		Physical comfort

ISO/IEC 25066:2016 Systems and software engineering furthermore specifies minimum requirements for different types of usability evaluations:

Table 2. Requirements for usability evaluations

Type of evaluation	Inspection	User observation		
		Observing user behaviour	Measuring user	Information from users

			performance and response	
Physical environment and facilities	N/A	Required	Required	Optional
Technical environment	Required	Required	Required	Required
Evaluation administration tools	Recommended	Recommended	Recommended	Recommended

As the COVINFORM dashboard is a technical environment, this task utilises the following methods to meet the following requirements and measure the following constructs:

Table 3. Requirements, methods, constructs, and data types

Requirement	Method	Construct	Data type
Inspection	Cognitive walkthrough for the web (Blackmon et al. 2002)	Effectiveness, efficiency, satisfaction, accessibility	Qualitative
Observing user behaviour	Concurrent think-aloud (Ericsson and Simon 1993) with exit interview	Effectiveness, efficiency, satisfaction, accessibility	Qualitative
Measuring user performance	Quantitative performance metrics	Effectiveness, efficiency	Quantitative
Measuring user response	System usability scale	Satisfaction	Quantitative
Information from users	Socio-demographic questionnaire	User attributes	Quantitative

The tests were conducted in four iterations:

- Iteration 1 (May 2021) comprised a requirements elicitation workshop
- Iterations 2 (October 2022) and 3 (July 2023) comprised two cognitive walkthrough for the web workshops
- Iteration 4 (September to October 2023) comprised concurrent think-aloud tests with supplementary quantitative questionnaires and qualitative interviews

An additional validation workshop was conducted at the project's final meeting in September 2023. This deliverable describes the purpose of the evaluation and the evaluation methods, then presents the results, along with interpretation and recommendations. It adopts the report structure recommended in *ISO/IEC 25066:2016 Systems and software engineering*.

2 Description of the object of evaluation

2.1 Formal name, release/version, and parts evaluated

COVINFORM Risk Assessment Dashboard release version as described in COVINFORM D2.9, “Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers”.

2.2 User groups for which the object is intended

The object is intended for the following user groups:

- Governmental organisations in public health and adjacent fields
- Civil society organisations in public health and adjacent fields
- Academics and other researchers in public health and adjacent fields, e.g., demography, economics, social epidemiology, sociology, psychology
- Journalists
- Secondary school teachers and students
- Social work practitioners engaged in non-clinical functions

2.3 Brief description of the object and its purpose

The COVINFORM Risk Assessment Dashboard provides access to secondary data on a wide range of health and socio-economic indicators relevant to the analysis of the pandemic. The indicators available in the release version are age & gender; airport traffic; airports; cargo; civic participation; corruption perception index; crime prevalence; digital access; digital literacy; doctors; education; employment by industry; food security; GDP; general government debt; government health spending; greenhouse gas emissions; hospital beds; housing concentration; immigrant population; immigration; income inequality; international trade; nurses; poverty (% of population); pollution; pre-existing health conditions; reduced income; residential care beds; seaborne passengers; social protection benefits; unemployment; urban vs. rural population; and vaccine affordability. These indicators are used to calculate risk scores entailing four components: threats (virus; likelihood of development); vulnerability (social, economic, informational); consequences (health; social; economic; environmental); and resilience (ability to recover, ability to adapt). The risk assessment methodology is described in D2.3, “Technical report”.

- The dashboard has the following functional sub-pages:
- Risk Assessment: displays overall risk scores and scores per component using an interactive map interface.
- Geospatial Plots: allows individual indicators to be mapped.
- Indicator Comparisons: allows individual indicators to be compared using scatter plots.
- COVID-19 trends: allows COVID-19 trends to be compared using time-series plots.
- Case Studies: allows qualitative data collected during the COVINFORM case studies (WP3) to be viewed.
- Knowledge Repository: provides access to COVID-19-related resources produced and/or curated by the COVINFORM project.

The dashboard’s full functionality is described in D2.9, “Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers”.

2.4 Intended context of use

The dashboard is best viewed using a personal computer, due to the complexity of its functions. Mobile usability is limited.

2.5 Expected impact of the object

The dashboard provides a novel service for both public health stakeholders and the wider scientific and educational community. It offers an interactive means of utilising the novel risk assessment methodology developed by the COVINFORM project, as well as access to a wide range of data points that are otherwise inaccessible in a single place.

2.6 Citations to market research for the object

D2.1, “Database containing different data sources”, includes a review of existing risk assessment models and dashboards.

3 Purpose of the evaluation

3.1 Description of the purpose

The purpose of the evaluation was twofold:

- To provide user input during an iterative development process, allowing for the continual improvement of the dashboard from the perspective of relevance and usability.
- To assess the functionality and usability of the final release.

3.2 Functions and components evaluated

All functions of the dashboard were evaluated.

4 Workshop 1 (May 2021): Requirements specification

4.1 Method

4.1.1 General: Type of evaluation used and sufficient information to replicate the evaluation

The workshop was a structured requirements elicitation for the dashboard, conducted prior to its development. To understand the needs of project partners, 'User Stories' were obtained from each participating project partner using a questionnaire prior to the workshop. User stories are used to capture (and discover) the desired product functionality and its value from the user's perspective. The value of employing user stories is that they compel both the developer and the end user to focus on understanding the why part of the user requirement. During the workshop, the developers presented the overall concept, and the user stories were then discussed in a structured format. Finally, mock-ups were presented. Following the workshop, TRI collated the list of high-level requirements identified in the focus groups for consensus with all partners (description, user, grade of importance, barriers and proposed solutions and a progress tracker).

4.1.2 Evaluators/participants

Total number and segmentation of evaluators/participants

Representatives from partners AUTRC, SAMUR, and UCSC (N=4) participated in the workshop.

Key characteristics of evaluators/participants and differences to the user population

The participants were aware of the project aims and generally aware of all project activities. In contrast, it is to be expected that the user population will not be aware of the project aims and activities.

Table of participants by characteristics

Table 4. Workshop 1 participants

Partner	Country	Role	Role
TRI	UK/Ireland	Developer	Facilitation
SINUS	Germany	Research (sociology)	Participant
SYNYO	Austria	Coordinator	Participant
AUTRC_1	Austria	Head of Response and Preparedness	Participant
AUTRC_2	Austria	Head of EMS & Psychosocial Support	Participant
SAMUR	Spain	Pre-hospital emergency healthcare provider	Participant
UCSC	Italy	Director of COVID-19 Clinical Unit	Participant

4.1.3 Tasks

Tasks used and task scenarios

The participants were asked to complete a “User Stories” questionnaire prior to the workshop (see Annex 1). The questionnaire gathered the following:

- User role and responsibilities.
- Data needs, scope, and intended outcomes.
- Data seeking and use on vulnerable groups during the pandemic
- Satisfaction/dissatisfaction with data available and reasons why
- Description of last time data on vulnerable groups was sought
- Level of technical knowledge needed to interpret the data sought
- Barriers to identifying vulnerable groups and deciding on actions that achieve meaningful outcomes
- Organisational definitions of “vulnerable” / “at-risk” groups

During the focus group itself, the following questions were discussed:

1. ‘As a [user role], I want to [conduct/respond/identify/gain insight], in [geographical area level], during [X] phase of the COVID-19, so I can achieve [outcome]’
2. ‘What data do you wish you had access to _____?’
3. ‘If I have indicator data to show [risk], I can respond by [action] to achieve [outcome]’
4. “The ideal risk assessment model would provide me with information on [situation/needs/population/proposed actions]”
5. “I envisage using the interactive software for [task], so I would need [requirements] in order for me to determine [outcome]”.

Selection criteria and sources of the tasks

The tasks were selected by the data science and design teams, to assist them in selecting datasets on the one hand, and considering user interfaces on the other.

Task data given to each evaluator/participant and/or inspector; criteria for task completion and abandonment for each task

Not applicable.

4.1.4 Evaluation environment

Physical and technical environments

The workshop was conducted online in May 2021.

Evaluation administration tools and administrators

The evaluation was administered, recorded, and analysed by TRI.

4.2 Procedure

4.2.1 Design of the evaluation

Description of the evaluation design

The workshop lasted approximately 2 hours. The agenda is shown in the following table. The full protocol used in the evaluation is provided in Annex 1.

Table 5. Workshop agenda

Time	Agenda item
T	Introductions and participant roles
T+5	Presentation: WP2 Overview [TRI]
T+20	Presentation: Overview of data identified and data sources [TRI: Technical Team]
T+30	Presentation: Overview of relevant indicators and composite indicators [TRI]
T+45	Review of partner User Requirement Stories (Appendix 1: User Requirements Questionnaire)
T+60	Pilot of platform [TRI Technical Team]
T+75	Breakout groups (4 participants from a range of stakeholders i.e., responders, researchers)
T+85	Breakout groups presentations
T+100	Discussion

Independent variables; predefined criteria for inspection or observation; measures used in evaluation; and/or operational criteria of criteria/measures

Not applicable.

Interaction between individuals taking part in each evaluation session

There were no specific rules related to interaction between individuals taking part in the session, aside from standard norms of professional conduct.

General instructions given to participants and specific instructions on tasks

Prior to each evaluation phase, participants were informed of the aim of the phase. Participants were not given specific instructions on tasks.

Sequence of activities for conducting the evaluation

The outline of activities is provided above under “Description of the evaluation design.”

4.2.2 Data to be collected

Usability defects in terms of deviations from predefined criteria

The workshop did not gather data on usability defects; rather, it consisted of a requirements elicitation.

Observed user behaviour; observed performance data; user-reported qualitative data; user-reported quantitative data

Not applicable.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Data analysis

Approach used for the analysis of observed, measured, or collected data

Following the workshop, TRI collated the list of high-level requirements identified in the focus groups for consensus with all partners (description, user, grade of importance, barriers and proposed solutions and a progress tracker)..

Differences in planned and collected data

No differences arose between the planned and actual data collection.

Portion of data used in the analysis

All data produced was used in the analysis.

Data scoring; data reduction; statistical analyses

Not applicable.

4.3.2 Presentation of the results

The questionnaires provided by the participants indicated the following participant roles, intended outcomes, and data seeking and use stories:

Table 6. Participant roles and intended outcomes

Participant	In my role, I want to:	So I can achieve:
AUTRC_1	Help that the impact of CoVid-19 is as low as possible regarding the (public) health, social, economical and psychological situation	Save lives.
AUTRC_2	To gain insight what exactly the needs of the vulnerable groups are	Go into future oriented planning; support developing solutions
SAMUR	Handle single and consensual procedures at first for the management of the suspected patient of COVID 19, procedures sufficiently consolidated and stable over time to avoid the uncertainty effect; Identify the infection early, in the cases attended; Have more protection material in stock; Train ourselves more in biological hazards	Better patient management; Comfort of the responders, avoiding uncertainties and stress in handling cases that pose a risk to them; Avoid risks; Transmit calm to the population; Have enough time and tools to deal with some social emergencies; Improve coordination with the next level of care (hospital)
UCSC	Build a questionnaire exploring at regional and country level the impact of the pandemic on health workers and their families, in its various dimensions: professional, physical and mental health	[No answer]

Table 7. Data seeking and use stories

Participant	Data typically sought	Satisfaction level and pain points
AUTRC_1	There is no formal data collection by AUTRC itself, so that every kind of verified, valid secondary data is welcome. Both quantitative data (e.g., dashboards of the Austrian Ministry of Health) and qualitative data (e.g., expert groups and with command staff of the ministry of the interior)	Dissatisfied: lack of valid data; lack of interoperability of data (standards for operationalization; harmonization between data collection points and periods; etc.)
AUTRC_2	Both quantitative data (e.g., dashboards of the Austrian Ministry of Health) and qualitative data (e.g., expert groups and with command staff of the ministry of the interior)	“As a crisis manager you take what you get”; Epidemiological data was generally good and nearly in real time (Austria is one of the few countries, that had an electronic system, where cases of infectious diseases of concern are centrally reported).
SAMUR	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC); Spanish Ministry of Health; European Medicines Agency; SAMUR own data regarding the psychologically affected medical first responders (sick, family losses, etc.); SAMUR data series of vulnerable people assisted (minors at risk, elderly at risk, gender violence, sexual assault, people with special emotional impact) (Service base); Information on population groups with higher risks (more probability of complications)	Satisfied with European institutional information websites; dissatisfied with Spanish Government information. Pain points: missing or wrong data on Spain; non-concordant sources on vaccine data; lack of SAMUR own data on occupational risk procedures.
UCSC	Publicly available data on monitoring COVID-19 on an Italian level, and on publicly available data on healthcare workers, primarily from Italian governmental institutions and associated research institutes.	Mostly satisfied. Pain points: the scientific literature is poor on the issue of mental health of HCW during the pandemic.

During the workshop itself, the following themes were discussed. The below table summarises the feedback provided during the discussion.

Table 8. Workshop discussion themes and feedback

Theme	Feedback
Preparedness	More future oriented crisis planning is needed
Planning	Main aim is to avoid risk and ensure that sufficient time is available to deal with social emergencies
Logistics	Crisis planning logistics are customised to roles, centres, and locations
Definitions	There should be shared definitions of “vulnerability” that are not limited to health vulnerability; currently, any harmonisation across organisations is generally informal
Interoperability	Data should be able to be shared across an organisation and (to an extent) between organisations
Asset registries	Registries are needed of resources and personnel

Interactive dashboards	Ability to integrate own data into the system would be positive
Ontologies used	NUTS
Trust in data	Satisfied with data from ECDC; however, other data sources are sometimes incomplete and/or contradictory
Availability of data	Data on social aspects of the pandemic are often not harmonised, not linked with epidemiological data, lack specificity, and fail to adequately cover key topics (e.g., vaccines)
Other at-risk groups	There is a need to identify population groups that may be at-risk, who do not fall into existing definitions of “vulnerability”
Information sharing with the public	There is a need to communicate to the public on consequences of the disease, social measures, and links to resources / sources of support within communities
Data interoperability	Different organisations in different countries may not define or operationalise concepts, or conduct measurement, in the same ways

4.3.3 Interpretation of results and recommendations

Interpretation of results

The users were all public health practitioners on a decision-making level within their organisations. Their responsibilities were concrete and significant: to optimise their organisations’ on-the-ground responses to public health crises, with the end goal of improving health outcomes and saving lives. Accordingly, they mostly required, sought, and used public health data from official sources. Their primary need was absolutely credible general population data on health factors, of the highest possible accuracy, consistency, and degree of granularity, as near to real-time as possible. A secondary need was general population data on related societal variables, e.g., social determinants of health and social and economic factors that mediate the impacts of public health emergencies (e.g., age, education, housing density, etc.). Another, unrelated need is better systems for the management of operational data within the users’ organisations, e.g., resources, personnel, logistics, procurement, etc.

Data disaggregation by different aspects of vulnerability is desirable (e.g., age, preexisting conditions, etc.). Harmonisation is desirable on concept level (e.g., definitions of vulnerability in different domains) and the data collection and processing level. Generally, satisfaction with public health data collected by European institutions is high, while satisfaction with public health data collected by national institutions, as well as civil society organisations, individual scientific studies, etc., varies greatly. Integration of analytics/modelling functions (e.g., via AI) could be interesting as they develop.

Recommendations

General recommendations were made on the level of good data management practices (e.g., use standardised and clearly defined and labelled data matrices, etc.). However, the most significant conclusion worked through the workshop was a change in target user group: from medical/public health practitioners to researchers, health communicators, health policymakers, journalists, educators, and the general public. This is because the type of data that are most actionable by public health practitioners are not available to the COVINFORM consortium due to regulatory and/or technical barriers: e.g., the consortium has no access to data from national and sub-national health

institutions, hospitals, long-term care facilities, etc. Gaining access to such data, taking inventory of its characteristics, assessing its quality, determining the degree to which it could be harmonised, etc., would itself be a major undertaking requiring dedicated personnel at numerous institutions – much less actually integrating such data into a single dashboard. This would be well outside the scope of a single work package within a Horizon project.

On the other hand, what is within scope for COVINFORM is to bring together a wide range of open-access data on COVID-19 and the numerous social factors that mediated its impact. While not actionable by clinical/medical practitioners at the decision-making level who must plan interventions to save lives, such data are of great value to those who must understand the disease within its broader social context: e.g., policymakers, decision-makers at civil society organisations outside the realm of clinical/medical practice, scientists and researchers, journalists, educators, and the general public. The workshop brought great clarity to this point, and assisted the developers and design team in pivoting to take better account of the needs of this target group, which were discussed during the following two workshops.

5 Workshops 2 & 3 (October 2022 and July 2023): Cognitive walkthrough for the web (CWW)

5.1 Method

5.1.1 General: Type of evaluation used and sufficient information to replicate the evaluation

The **cognitive walkthrough**, which is based on the *theory of facilitated learning by exploration* in the field of human-computer interactions, was developed as a means of evaluating “walk-up-and-use” interfaces, i.e., interfaces that do not require special training (Polson & Lewis 1990; cf. Lewis et al. 1990). It is a review process in which the developers and designers of an interface present the product to a group of peers representative of the stakeholder group for which the interface is intended, who then evaluate it using structured tasks and criteria (Wharton et al. 1994).

The developers of the cognitive walkthrough technique acknowledge that it is first and foremost a method of evaluating ease of learning, and that “use of the Cognitive Walkthrough as the only method for evaluating an interface would push design trade-offs in an interface in the direction of ease of learning”; they thus recommend pairing the cognitive walkthrough with other evaluation techniques throughout the development process (Wharton et al. 1993, pg. 4). For this reason, the cognitive walkthrough is supplemented with concurrent think-aloud (CTA) tests.

In part due to the recognition of such trade-offs, the cognitive walkthrough method has evolved over the years, generating several variations. The third variation on the original authors’ cognitive walkthrough method – referred to as CW3 – responds to criticisms by adopting a highly structured flow, consisting of five sequences of steps (adapted from Wharton et al. 1993, pg. 2-3):

1. Define inputs to the walkthrough
 - a. Who are the target users?
 - b. What tasks will be analysed? Note that the benchmark tasks should be as realistic as possible, and must include descriptions of context.
 - c. What is the proper action sequence for each task, and how is it described? A rule of thumb is that the actions should be described at the same level of detail as a basic tutorial.
 - d. How is the interface defined or implemented? The cognitive walkthrough process can be conducted using mock-ups or alpha implementations.
2. Convene the analysts. These peers can include other developers/designers/engineers, but also other stakeholders. One peer should act as a facilitator and another should be responsible for taking memos; the others can contribute insight from their domains of expertise in a relatively open manner.
3. Walk through the action sequence for each task
 - a. Tell a credible story, considering:
 - i. Will the user try to achieve the right effect?
 - ii. Will the user notice that the correct action is available?
 - iii. Will the user associate the correct action with the effect they are trying to achieve?

- iv. If the correct action is performed, will the user see that progress is being made toward the solution of their task? Note that the worst-case scenario here is receiving no feedback on the status of the task.
4. Record critical information
 - a. User knowledge requirements: should be defined at the onset of the walkthrough as a whole and at the onset of each task.
 - b. Assumptions about the user population: should be defined at the onset of the walkthrough.
 - c. Notes about side issues and design changes: should be recorded throughout the walkthrough.
 - d. The credible success story, founded on common features of success, e.g.:
 - i. Users may know what effect they want to achieve.
 - ii. Users may know what actions are available.
 - iii. Users may know what actions are appropriate for the effect they are trying to achieve.
 - iv. Users may know things are going OK / as expected after an action.
***Note that failure stories are also a part of cognitive walkthroughs. Common failure points can include users not knowing prerequisite actions or states; users not associating the required action with the desired effect, in context; users not being aware of certain functions; users confusing two or more functions; users misrecognising visual elements in the UI; users not knowing that certain follow-up actions are needed; users not knowing how to determine whether a task was successful; users “timing out”; users being unable to physically execute an action (e.g., holding down three keys simultaneously); and users being unaware that terminator actions are required (e.g., pushing the pound key after entering a number).*
 5. Revise the interface to fix the problems

Other teams of developers and HCI scholars have proposed variations on the original cognitive walkthrough. The heuristic walkthrough (HW; Nelson & Molich 1990), for instance, consists of two phases: phase 1 follows the question flow of CW3, while phase 2 is a free exploration of the system supported by “heuristics” derived from the heuristic evaluation method. The streamlined cognitive walkthrough (SCW; Spencer 2000) trims CW3’s five questions down to two:

1. Will users know what to do at this step?
2. If users do the right thing, will they know that they did so and are making progress toward their goal?

The enhanced cognitive walkthrough (ECW; Bligard & Osvalder 2013) takes the opposite approach, supplementing CW3 by adding two sequences of analysis questions, one sequence on analysis of functions and one sequence on analysis of operations (pg. 7-8):

1. Analysis of functions
 - a. Will the user know that the evaluated function is available? Does the user expect, on the basis of previously given indications that the function exists in the machine?
 - b. Will the user be able to notice that the function is available? Does the machine give clues that show that the function exists?

- c. Will the user associate the clues with the function? Can the user's expectations and the machine's indications coincide?
 - d. Will the user get sufficient feedback when using the function? Does the machine give information that the function has been chosen and to what position the user is in the interaction?
 - e. Will the user get sufficient feedback to understand that the function has been fully performed? Does the user understand, after the performed sequence of actions, that the right function has been performed?
2. Analysis of operations
- a. Will the user try to achieve the right goals of the operation? Does the user expect, on the basis of previously given indications, what is to be performed?
 - b. Will the user be able to notice that the action of the operation is available? Does the machine give clues that show that the action is available and how to perform it?
 - c. Will the user associate the action of the operation with the right goal of the operation? Can the user's assumed operation and the machine's indications coincide?
 - d. Will the user be able to perform the correct action? Do the abilities of the user match the demands by the machine?
 - e. Will the user get sufficient feedback to understand that the action is performed and the goal is achieved? Does the user understand, after the performed operation, that he/she has done right?

The ECW furthermore suggests utilising a structured typology of problems during the analysis: for instance, in the example case study of testing a home-care ventilator, the following problem types are identified (pg. 8):

- User (U): The problem is due to the user's experience and knowledge, possibly because the user is accustomed to different equipment.
- Hidden (H): The interface gives no indications that the function is available or how it should be used.
- Text and icon (T): Placement, appearance and content can easily be misinterpreted or misunderstood.
- Sequence (S): Functions and operations have to be performed in an unnatural sequence.
- Physical demands (P): The interface sets too high demands on users' physical speed, motoric skill and force.
- Feedback (F): The interface gives unclear indications of what the user is doing or has done.

Note that the analysis questions and problem types identified in the ECW are not all relevant to purely online platform use cases: e.g., the operations analysis question "do the abilities of the user match the demands by the machine" and the problem type "physical demands" are unlikely to arise in an online platform use case, except with regard to vision-impaired users.

The need to more precisely tailor the CW method to online use cases gave rise to another variant, the cognitive walkthrough for the web (CWW). CWW is based on a learning model developed with reference to online search, CoLiDeS or Comprehension-based Linked Model of Deliberate Search (Kitajima, Blackmon, & Polson 2000). CoLiDeS holds that "problem solving processes, guided by users' goals and *information scent*, drive users' information seeking or search behaviors when exploring a new website or carrying out a novel task on a familiar website" (Blackmon et al. 2002, pg. 464). The

CWW tailors the CW3 sequence of testing steps to tasks specifically related to online information seeking and search behaviours, including through the integration of analytical techniques suited to text-based interface analysis (pg. 465-466):

1. Compile a set of realistic user goals and intended selections, optionally from the perspective of defined user personas. This step corresponds to step 1a to 1c in the CW3.
2. Use latent semantic analysis (LSA), a technique in natural language processing, to estimate semantic similarity of user goals and page/subregion/widget headings/link labels. This “pre-analytical” step extends step 1d in the CW3. Blackmon et al. (2002) suggest using the LSA website developed by the University of Colorado Boulder (<http://lsa.colorado.edu/>), which can generate estimates of the semantic similarity of the user goals and the heading/link labels in cosine form. Note that this analysis requires some familiarity with the theory behind latent semantic analysis. In principle, other quantitative and/or qualitative semantic analytical methods could be substituted.
3. Identify problematic headings/link labels. This step also extends step 1d in the CW3.
4. Find goals-specific problems. This step picks up step 3a/4a of the CW3, the “credible success story.” CWW modifies the CW3 sequence of analysis questions as follows:
 - a. Will the correct action be made sufficiently evident for the user?
 - b. Will the user connect the correct action’s description with what he or she is trying to do?
 - i. Will the user correct subregion of the page with the goal using heading information and her understanding of the site’s page layout conventions?
 - ii. Will the user connect the goal with the correct widget in the attended-to subregion of the page using link labels and other kinds of descriptive information?
 - c. Will the user interpret the system’s response to the chosen action correctly?

Like the ECW, the CWW also suggests identifying specific types of problems relevant to the goals under evaluation, e.g.:

- Unfamiliar headings/link labels: the user does not know what the label means
- Confusable headings/link labels: the label could easily be confused with another label
- Goal-specific competing headings/link labels: the similarity of an incorrect label to the goal is greater than the similarity of the correct label to the goal

The efficacy of the CWW in predicting actual user behaviour has been tested experimentally, e.g. by checking the first-click success rate of the unfamiliar, confusable, and competing labels identified in the CWW; the method’s predictive power varies contextually, but has generally been found to be good (Larson & Czerwinski 1998; Blackmon et al. 2002).

5.1.2 Evaluators/participants

Total number and segmentation of evaluators/participants

The workshops were conducted by a gender-balanced interdisciplinary team of project partners. A representative from each consortium partner (N=16) participated in Workshop 2 (October 2022), whereas a smaller group of N=5 partners were chosen to participate in Workshop 3 (July 2023), which represented several project roles and end-user fields.

Key characteristics of evaluators/participants and differences to the user population

The participants were aware of the project aims and generally aware of all project activities. Awareness of the specific aims, functions, and components of the object evaluated varied widely. In contrast, it is to be expected that users outside the consortium will not be aware of the project aims and activities. Hence, the individual usability testing will be conducted with external users completely unfamiliar with the project.

Table of participants by characteristics

Table 9. Workshop 2 participants (October 2022)

Partner	Country	Field	Role
SINUS	Germany	Research (sociology)	Facilitation
TRI	UK/Ireland	Developer	Facilitation
SYNYO	Austria	Coordinator	Facilitation
MDA	Israel	Health care	Participant
SAMUR	Spain	Health care	Participant
UCSC	Italy	Health care	Participant
KEMEA	Greece	Security	Participant
FS	Portugal	Research (psychology)	Participant
AUTRC	Austria	Health care	Participant
MDI	UK	Journalism	Participant
SNCRR	Romania	Health care	Participant
UANTWERPEN	Belgium	Research (sociology)	Participant
SAPIENZA	Italy	Research (economics)	Participant
URJC	Spain	Research (epidemiology)	Participant
SU	UK	Research (geography)	Participant
UGOT	Sweden	Research (communications)	Participant

Table 10. Workshop 3 participants (July 2023)

Organisation	Country	Field	Role
SINUS	Germany	Research (sociology)	Facilitation
TRI	UK/Ireland	Developer	Facilitation
SYNYO	Austria	Coordinator	Facilitation
FS	Portugal	Research (psychology)	Participant
AUTRC	Austria	Health care	Participant

SAPIENZA	Italy	Research (economics)	Participant
SU	UK	Research (geography)	Participant

5.1.3 Tasks

Tasks used and task scenarios

The following tasks were identified during the workshops.

Table 11. Workshop 2 tasks (October 2022)

Task	Description	Scenario (use flow)
1	<i>Risk Assessment: Report the overall score within a given country in 2020</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Choose year - Choose aggregation function - Navigate to map - Click on chosen country
2	<i>Geospatial Plots: Find the education time series within a given country, disaggregated by sex</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Choose dataset - Choose "Disaggregations: Sex" - Navigate to map - Click on chosen country
2	<i>Indicator Comparisons: Check the correlation between the data points "GDP" and "Doctors" in 2020</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Choose first dataset - Choose second dataset - Select date - Navigate to chart
3	<i>COVID-19 Trends: Compare the data points "Daily Cases & Deaths" and "Excess Deaths" for two countries</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Choose first dataset - Choose second dataset - Choose first country - Check box "Compare Trends from Two Countries" - Choose second country - Navigate to chart

Table 12. Workshop 3 tasks (July 2023)

Task	Description	Scenario (use flow)
1	<i>Identify the "lessons learned" from the case study in Greece</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Choose case study location - Navigate to "Lessons Learned" section

Selection criteria and sources of the tasks

The workshop participants identified one task per functional section of the dashboard, judged relevant to the likely target users. Workshop 2 focused on the sections "Risk Assessment", "Geospatial Plots", "Indicator Comparisons", and "COVID-19 Trends". Workshop 3 focused on the section "Case Studies". As the "Case Studies" section is straightforward on a functional level, only one task was identified. The "Knowledge Repository" section was not functional at the time of testing.

Task data given to each evaluator/participant and/or inspector; criteria for task completion and abandonment for each task

Not applicable.

5.1.4 Evaluation environment

Physical and technical environments

Workshop 3 was conducted in person at a COVINFORM Consortium Meeting in Athens, Greece on 10 October 2022. Workshop 2 was conducted online on 20 July 2023. Both workshops were recorded and transcribed.

Evaluation administration tools and administrators

The evaluation was administered, recorded, and analysed by SINUS.

5.2 Procedure

5.2.1 Design of the evaluation

Description of the evaluation design

Each cognitive walkthrough lasted approximately 1.5 hours. The agenda is shown in the following tables. The full protocol template used in the evaluation itself is provided in Annex 2.

Table 13. CWW agenda

Time	Phase	Phase name
T	A	Confirm target user groups
T+10	A	Confirm assumptions about target users
T+20	A	Confirm user knowledge requirements
T+30	B	Define user tasks
T+60	C	Identification of user-task-specific problems
T+90	End	Conclusion

Rather than integrating a latent semantic analysis (LSA) into the CWW agenda, a qualitative semantic analysis of the headings/link labels on the platform has been performed by a smaller sub-set of partners (SINUS, TRI, SYNYO). This fulfils the intended purpose of assessing the semantic similarity of page/subregion/widget headings/link labels – e.g., their potential confusability.

Independent variables; predefined criteria for inspection or observation; measures used in evaluation; and/or operational criteria of criteria/measures

Phase A and B of the walkthroughs did not entail inspection/observation/evaluation.

During Phase C, in accordance with the CWW format (Blackmon et al. 2002), for each task, the participants discussed the following “credible success story” criteria:

1. Will the user try to achieve the right effect?

2. Will the user notice that the correct action is available?
3. Will the user associate the correct action with the effect they are trying to achieve?
4. If the correct action is performed, will the user see that progress is being made toward the solution of their task? Note that the worst-case scenario here is receiving no feedback on the status of the task.

Interaction between individuals taking part in each evaluation session

There were no specific rules related to interaction between individuals taking part in the session, aside from standard norms of professional conduct.

General instructions given to participants and specific instructions on tasks

Prior to each evaluation phase, participants were informed of the aim of the phase. Participants were not given specific instructions on tasks.

Sequence of activities for conducting the evaluation

The outline of activities is provided above under “Description of the evaluation design.” The full protocol template used in the evaluation is provided in Annex 2. The protocol generally follows the CWW format suggested by Blackmon et al. (2002), borrowing certain elements as needed from the CW3 (Wharton et al. 1993) and ECW (Bligard & Osvalder 2013).

5.2.2 Data to be collected

Usability defects in terms of deviations from predefined criteria

Phases A and B did not collect data on usability defects, nor deviations from predefined criteria; rather, these phases collected data on target user groups and knowledge requirements, then identified relevant tasks for the evaluation itself.

During Phases C, a structured problem typology was utilised that synthesises the CWW with problem types proposed in the ECW (Bligard & Osvalder 2013):

- User (U): The problem is due to the user’s experience and knowledge.
- Hidden (H): The interface gives no indications that the function is available or how it should be used.
- Text and icon, including headings/link labels (T): Placement, appearance and content can easily be misinterpreted or misunderstood. For sub-categories, see above.
- Sequence (S): Functions and operations have to be performed in an unnatural sequence.
- Feedback (F): The interface gives unclear indications of what the user is doing or has done.
- Other (O)

During the qualitative semantic analysis of the platform, the headings/link labels were checked against the task descriptions, and unfamiliar, confusable, or goal-specific competing labels were flagged using a grid. Following Blackmon et al. (2002), the following categories of text and icon problem were identified:

- Unfamiliar text/icon: the user does not know what the label means
- Confusable text/icon: the label could easily be confused with another label
- Goal-specific competing text/icon: the similarity of an incorrect label to the goal is greater than the similarity of the correct label to the goal

- Other

Observed user behaviour; observed performance data; user-reported qualitative data; user-reported quantitative data

Not applicable.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Data analysis

Approach used for the analysis of observed, measured, or collected data

The semantic legibility of the headings, link labels, and other critical text was assessed quantitatively (percentage of semantic pairs featuring problems of certain types) and qualitatively (description of the errors, generated through discussion).

The “credible success story” criteria per task (Phase C) were assessed quantitatively (percentage of criteria featuring a potential problem) and qualitatively (description of the use flow and any potential problems, generated through discussion).

Differences in planned and collected data

No differences arose between the planned and actual data collection.

Portion of data used in the analysis

All data produced was used in the analysis.

Data scoring; data reduction; statistical analyses

Not applicable.

5.3.2 Presentation of the results

Confirmation of target user groups, assumptions about target users, and knowledge requirements

As mentioned in the workshop 1 presentation of results, that workshop led to a pivot away from clinical practitioners as a target group, as the consortium is not legally or technically able to access the kind of health data that is actionable when planning health interventions. During these workshops 2 and 3, that pivot was confirmed. In both workshops, the participants agreed that the user groups are the following:

- Governmental organisations active in public health and adjacent fields
- Civil society organisations active in public health and adjacent fields – however, not necessarily departments that do clinical work
- Academics and other researchers in public health and adjacent fields, e.g., demography, economics, social epidemiology, sociology, psychology
- Journalists
- Non-clinical social work practitioners with an interest in understanding the context of societal crises: e.g., social workers, youth workers, etc. – note language could be a barrier
- Secondary school teachers and students – note language could be a barrier

In both workshops, all participants furthermore agreed upon the following assumptions about the target users and their knowledge requirement:

- Users can be expected to be generally familiar with the concept of quantitative indicators
- Users can be expected to be generally familiar with what the COVID-19 is
- Users must read English on a comparatively high level – this could be a barrier for some user groups, such as secondary school students.
- Users cannot be expected to have specialist knowledge in public health, social epidemiology, or a similar field

Usability defects and potential usability problems likely to arise: Credible success stories per task

The participants talked through each of the tasks identified in Phase B, assessing each of the “credible success story” criteria developed by Bligard & Osvalder (2013).

The workshops found that of 25 total items, 84% featured no potential usability problems, whereas 16% did feature potential usability problems.

Table 14. Evaluation of credible success stories per task

Code	Problem type	Count	% of total
NA	No usability problems	19	76%
U	The problem is due to the user’s experience and knowledge.	0	0%
H	The interface gives no indications that the function is available or how it should be used.	0	0%
T	Placement, appearance and content can easily be misinterpreted or misunderstood. For sub-categories, see semantic analysis.	2	8%
S	Functions and operations have to be performed in an unnatural sequence.	0	0%
F	The interface gives unclear indications of what the user is doing or has done.	1	4%
O	Other	3	12%
Total items		25	100%
Total issues		6	24%

The full findings of the task evaluations are included in Annex 4 (T2.5_CWW_credible_success_stories).

Usability defects and potential usability problems likely to arise: Semantic analysis

The semantic analysis utilised a matrix by which all link labels present on each page were cross-checked for potential confusion or semantic clashes.

The workshop 1 analysis found that of 472 total label pairs, 98% were understandable and did not clash, whereas 2% were either potentially confusing or potentially clashing. The specific breakdown of problem types, utilising categories developed by Blackmon et al. (2002), is as follows:

Table 15. Semantic analysis findings

Code	Problem type	Count	% of total
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OK	No semantic issue	472	98%
UT	Unfamiliar text/icon: the user does not know what the label means	0	0%
CT	Confusable text/icon: the label could easily be confused with another label	8	2%
GSCT	Goal-specific competing text/icon: the similarity of an incorrect label to the goal is greater than the similarity of the correct label to the goal	0	0%
O	Other	0	0%
Total pairs		480	100%
Total issues		8	2%

The full findings of the semantic analysis are included in Annex 4 (T2.5_CWW_semantic_analysis).

5.3.3 Interpretation of results and recommendations

Interpretation of results

The workshop participants generally agreed that the dashboard was useful and well-designed. The aesthetic dimension received praise as being simple and contemporary, without looking too technical or being overloaded with graphics.

Two concrete usability errors were identified:

- During workshop 2, the “COVID-19 Trends” sub-page was not fully functional – choosing some datasets produced error messages.
- During workshop 3, scrolling was not functional within the geospatial displays.

The only semantic issue found was potential confusion between the “Risk Assessment” and “Geospatial Plots” function labels. Both functions utilise geospatial plotting: the former of risk assessment and model component scores (e.g., compound indicators), the latter of individual simple indicators. However, the labels themselves do not make this clear.

At the time of testing, critical accompanying information was missing: e.g., a splash page explaining the dashboard in simple language, a methodology page, information boxes indicating how each function should be used, and information on the indicators themselves (description of relevance, measurement unit, data source). The participants provided numerous specific recommendations for major and minor improvements, which are summarised in the following section.

Recommendations

The following errors must be resolved:

- During workshop 2, the “COVID-19 Trends” sub-page regularly produced numerous error messages and must be debugged.
- During workshop 3, scrolling within the geospatial data displays was often buggy, requiring the user to reduce the overall display size. Scrolling must be debugged.

The following recommendations were made in workshop 2:

- To avoid confusion with the “Risk Assessment” function (which is also displayed geospatially), consider renaming “Geospatial Plots”, e.g., as “Geospatial Indicator Plots”, “Indicator Maps”, or some variant that makes it clear that individual indicators are displayed.
- A splash page should be added with a description of the dashboard and its intended uses, and links to the data sources.
- A methodology section should be added, indicating how the risk score is calculated, why it is calculated in that way. If good methodological explanations are added, the dashboard could be used as a tool for teaching about composite indicators composition, risk modelling, etc.
- The methodology page should also give a brief description of why each indicator is significant in a COVID-19 context.
- We must be careful that our data is not misinterpreted / misused. The dashboard should clearly acknowledge its sources and limitations.
- We must assume that users are not familiar with technical concepts such as arithmetic vs. geometric aggregation functions. Informational notes must be added, either to the main pages or in a separate “how-to” page.
- The unit of measurement and data source should be clearly shown per indicator.
- Data export in CSV format would be helpful (if allowed by the data source terms of use).
- Chart export would be helpful.

The following recommendations were made in workshop 3:

- Development work between October 2022 and July 2023 had mainly focused on the functional areas – in particular the “Case Studies” function. Accordingly, explanatory pages or notes on overall project information and methodology had not yet been added. This was recommended again in workshop 3 as a high priority.
- The explanatory page could include tips on which functions might be useful for different user groups: e.g., “for researchers”, “for policymakers”, “for teachers and students”, etc.
- The explanatory page should include a citation in APA format (as well as citations for individual data sources).
- The unit of measurement and data source had been added per indicator within the geospatial displays, however, scrolling must be debugged (see above).
- Although “Risk Assessment” is the unique value proposition of the tool, it is also the more complex function. One workshop participant suggested a “walkthrough”-type structure wherein users are first introduced to individual indicators, then to the risk model dimensions (composite indicator), then to the full risk model.
- With regard to the “Case Studies” function, consider adding an explanatory splash page or note: what was the context and purpose of the case studies as a whole (participant: *“like the word indicator, the word case study means different things to different people in different disciplines. We should specify what we mean by this.”*)
- With regard to the “Case Studies” function: at the time of testing, the socio-ecological systems framework diagram was prominently displayed above the case study information. Workshop participants thought this could confuse users, as a high level of background knowledge is needed to interpret the diagram. Participants agreed that the diagram should come at the bottom of the page, or in a pop-up tab, and should be accompanied by an information box if it is used.

- With regard to the “Case Studies” function: at the time of testing, not all buttons were labelled (i.e., the speech bubble buttons used to display citations).
- With regard to the “Case Studies” function: the illustrations should be checked for inclusiveness and diversity. There was some concern that the representations might be taken literally: e.g., that the image of a health care worker in a protective suit might link to a quotation specifically from a crisis first responder (rather than, e.g., a nurse at a general practitioner’s office).
- The concept of customisable weighting of indicator components in the risk assessment model was discussed, but the consensus is that this would not be useful to the average user, would be complex to implement, and would multiply the risk of drawing inaccurate conclusions from the data.

6 Individual usability testing (September and October 2023): Concurrent think-aloud (CTA)

6.1 Method

6.1.1 General: Type of evaluation used and sufficient information to replicate the evaluation

Think-aloud methods are a well-established method of studying “task-based cognitive processes” in general, and human-computer interactions in particular (McDonald et al. 2012, pg. 3). In response to the criticism that thinking aloud is itself a cognitive process that violates the ecological validity of the task, Ericsson and Simon (1993) systematically investigated and categorised variations on the method, identifying two basic types: concurrent think-aloud (CTA), during which research participants narrate their cognitive processes while undertaking tasks, and retrospective think-aloud (RTA), during which participants describe their cognitive processes after undertaking tasks. Academic researchers and usability practitioners surveyed by McDonald et al. (2012) rated concurrent think-aloud tests as a more effective means of identifying usability problems and determining the root causes of such problems than post-task interviews, quantitative performance metrics (e.g., task completion rate, time on task, etc.), behavioural observation, or eye-tracking (pg. 15), though many also concurred that think-aloud tests are more suited to formative than summative evaluations (insofar as one aim is to provide feedback that can be used to improve the system, rather than simply measuring its quality).

In the “classic” concurrent and retrospective think-aloud methods, based on Ericsson and Simon’s work, a single user undertakes the target tasks. Ericsson and Simon recommend taking standardised measures to maximise the utility and neutrality of the narrative data elicited: these include offering warm-up / practice opportunities; keeping written scripts as neutral as possible; keeping evaluator probes as general as possible (e.g., so-called Level 1 probes such as “keep talking”, rather than so-called Level 2 or 3 probes such as specific instructions or questions about thought processes); and generally minimising interaction between the evaluator and the user. Among the alternatives to classic concurrent think-aloud method are “constructive interaction” or “co-discovery” approaches, in which two (or more) users undertake the target tasks together (Miyake 1986; Barnum 2010); “speech communication” approaches, in which an extended range of naturalistic communication cues are used by the evaluator to help the participant keep talking (e.g., giving feedback in the form of “um-hum” or “acknowledgement tokens” and/or briefly asking participants to clarify statements) (Boren & Ramsey 2000); and “coaching” or “active intervention” approaches, in which the evaluator provides verbal feedback and asks specific follow-up questions about the participant’s testing activities and/or underlying thought processes (Dumas & Redish 1999).

As a number of researchers have observed, neither instructional texts nor usability testers in the field universally adhere to Ericsson and Simon’s recommended practices (Boren & Ramsey 2000; Nørgaard and K. Hornbæk 2006; Shi 2008). For instance, numerous instructional texts recommend that evaluators use specific probes/interventions (i.e., other than “keep talking”) (McDonald et al. 2012). This can be due to the need to adapt to cultural or personality characteristics of users (Clemmensen et al. 2009), the need to maintain the test flow, or because classic think-aloud narratives tend to be shallowly descriptive, lack relevance to the “why” of usability problems, and lack actionability with regard to iterative improvement (Makri et al. 2011). Of professionals surveyed by McDonald et al. (2012), academic researchers were equally likely to adhere to Ericsson and Simon’s guidelines, while

usability practitioners were notably more likely to take a flexible approach; the latter in particular are likely to intervene when users are stuck on tasks, ask for help, mistakenly think tasks are complete, skip over features of interest to the evaluators, or complete tasks in “unexpected” ways (pg. 14).

Among professionals surveyed by McDonald et al. (2012), classic concurrent think-aloud tests are used much more frequently than constructive interaction approaches (96% vs. 22% among academic researchers and 98% vs. 36% among usability practitioners) (pg. 8). The argued benefits of classic concurrent approaches are efficiency, relative ease of recruiting participants, relative ease of explaining the tasks and method itself to participants, and relative ease of conveying findings to stakeholders; the argued benefits of constructive interaction approaches are that they are more ecologically valid and less “inquisitive,” and that the conversational data that they elicit are less artificial than a narrative monologue elicited from a solitary user (pg. 9). Several studies have sought to experimentally compare the test characteristics of different think-aloud protocols. Alshammari et al. (2015), for instance, compared CTA with RTA on three levels: success in revealing usability problems while completing tasks on a ticket booking website; task performance; and participant satisfaction with the test protocol. Both CTA and RTA evaluations followed Ericsson and Simon’s guidelines. Contrary to Alshammari et al.’s hypothesis, CTA proved more effective in uncovering usability problems.

Likewise, Olmstead-Hawala et al. (2010) compared classic CTA, in which Ericsson and Simon’s guidelines were followed, with “speech communication” and “coaching” approaches, finding that the participants in the coaching tests were significantly more likely to accurately complete test tasks on the U.S. Census Bureau website, as well as to express satisfaction with the website. Olmstead-Hawala et al. state that “this is detrimental in a typical usability study because the coaching injects bias into the results: the results are skewed toward better performance than the participant would have achieved without help” (pg. 2388). However, no such biasing effect was found for the “speech communication” approach. Accordingly, a classic concurrent think-aloud protocol, supplemented by speech communication insights, has been utilised.

6.1.2 Evaluators/participants

Total number and segmentation of evaluators/participants

The CTA tests were conducted with a gender-balanced sample of representatives of the following target groups. The sample size is based on Alshammari et al.’s (2010) finding that a group of N=5 participants were able to find 80-85% of the website usability problems reported by a total group of N=30 participants, whereas N=12 participants were able to find 100% of the reported usability problems.

Table 16. Target groups, recruitment procedures and inclusion and exclusion criteria

Target groups	Recruiting procedures	Inclusion & exclusion criteria	Sample
Academics	Each partner organisation recruited participants within their network, with clear instructions on the target group	Each participant needs to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • have a minimum knowledge of statistics • speak English • work within the fields of crisis 	N=5
Government employees			N=4
Employees of NGOs or CSOs			N=2
Journalists			N=1

		management, public health, and community wellbeing	
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Key characteristics of evaluators/participants

It was expected that users outside the consortium would not be aware of the project aims and activities. The task was intended to elicit input from this population.

Differences between sample and the user population

The sample was intended to represent the three major user groups identified at the project start.

6.1.3 Tasks

Tasks used and task scenarios

The following tasks were identified during the concurrent think-aloud evaluations.

Table 17. CTA tasks

Task	Description	Scenario (use flow)
1	<i>Find out what the tab "Risk Assessment" is about and how to correctly use the tool.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select "Risk Assessment" - Click on the information button
2	<i>Find out the Risk assessment for Sweden in a domain that is relevant to your field and find the country's rank.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select "Risk Assessment" - Select Year and Aggregation function - Select domain - Select country "Sweden" - Read "Rank"
3	<i>Find out what the tab "Geospatial Plots" is about and how to correctly use the tool.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select "Geospatial Plots" - Click on the information button
4	<i>Find the digital access rate for households in rural areas in Italy, as of 2019</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select "Geospatial Plots" - Select data set - Select household type - Select year - Click on Italy and read the number
5	<i>Compare the government health spending and vaccine affordability and download the chart. Make sure you have all relevant information to use the tool.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select "Indicator Comparisons" - Click on the information button - Select first data set "Government Health Spending" - Select second data set "Vaccine Affordability" - Click on "Download Chart"
6	<i>Compare the developments of Vaccination Rates and Number of Excess Deaths between France and Spain. Make sure you have all relevant information to use the tool.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select "COVID-19 Trends" - Click on the information button - Select first data set "COVID-19 Vaccination Rates" - Select second data set "Excess Deaths" - Select Country

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click on “Compare Trends from Two Countries” - Select second country
7	Find the case study about Greece and find a quote about community. Make sure you have all relevant information to navigate the website.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select “Case Study” - Click on the information button - Select “Greece” - Scroll down to lessons learnt - Click on the speech bubble saying “Community is...”
8	Find a COVINFORM output relevant to your field of interest. Make sure you have all relevant information to navigate the website.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select “Knowledge Repositors” - Click on the information button - Select document type “Covinform Output” - Select topic of interest - Select initiative

Selection criteria and sources of the tasks

The tasks were based on a set of tasks initially identified by the cognitive walkthrough participants and platform developers as relevant to the target groups and performable within a comparatively short testing session. The initial selection was modified and expanded by SINUS and TRI to better reflect new functions made available between the date of the workshops and the date of the usability testing.

Task data given to each evaluator/participant and/or inspector

Not applicable.

Criteria for task completion and abandonment for each task

Criteria for task completion: as soon as the user believes the task has been completed.

Criteria for task abandonment: as soon as the user decides to abandon the task.

6.1.4 Evaluation environment

Physical and technical environments

As with the CWW, the CTA was conducted via teleconference, recorded, and transcribed.

Evaluation administration tools and administrators

The evaluation was administered, recorded, and analysed by SINUS.

6.2 Procedure

6.2.1 Design of the evaluation

Description of the evaluation design

The concurrent think-aloud test design is shown in the following tables. The full protocol template used in the evaluation itself is provided in Annex 3.

Table 18. CTA Agenda

Time	Phase	Phase name
------	-------	------------

T	A	Description and warm-up task
T+5	B	User tasks
T+20	C	Exit interview
T+35	D	System usability scale and socio-demographic questionnaire

The protocol template is provided in Annex 3. In keeping with Ericsson and Simon’s guidelines, the protocol began with a warm-up during which the think-aloud concept was concisely explained and the participant was given the chance to practice thinking aloud while completing a simple task (e.g., searching for a credible information source on Google). The participant was then given a selection of written scripts describing tasks. The task selection mirrors that used.

The test protocol was designed to take ca. 20-25 minutes. The participants were also asked to conduct a ca. 5-10 minute exit interview, for a total length-of-interview of ca. 30 to maximum 40 minutes. The exit interview began with a few open questions about overall usability, and ended with the administration of the system usability scale (SUS) questionnaire, which consists of nine general usability questions scored using a five-point Likert-type scale, as well as a socio-demographic questionnaire. After completing these questionnaires, the participants were given the option of sharing their SUS scores with the evaluator and explaining why they scored particular SUS items the way that they did; however, this was not mandatory

Independent variables, predefined criteria for inspection or observation, measures used in evaluation, and operational criteria of criteria/measures

Part A did not entail inspection/observation/evaluation.

Part B was recorded, transcribed, and coded for usability problem types, user attitudes, and quantitative performance metrics provided in Section 6.2.2.

Answers on parts C and D were recorded using a spreadsheet, entailing ordinal and categorical variables provided in Section 6.2.2.

Interaction between individuals taking part in each evaluation session

The scripts are kept as neutral as possible. During the test itself, the evaluators were instructed to minimise their interaction with the participants, whenever possible restricting their probes to Ericsson and Simon’s Level 1 and 2 prompts and restrained “acknowledgement tokens”. Level 3 prompts were only used if absolutely necessary to the successful completion of the test.

- Levels 1 and 2: reminders to “keep talking” and acknowledgement tokens (e.g., “um-hmm”)
- Level 3: questions about specific actions or the thoughts behind them (e.g., “why did you click on that purple tab?”)

General instructions given to participants

The participants were instructed to narrate their actions, cognitive processes, and reactions while undertaking tasks, freely and in detail.

Specific instructions on tasks

As the tasks are all relatively self-explanatory, users were not provided with task-specific instructions unless they specifically asked.

Sequence of activities for conducting the evaluation

The outline of activities is provided above under “Description of the evaluation design.” The full protocol template used in the evaluation is provided in Annex 3.

6.2.2 Data to be collected

Usability defects in terms of deviations from predefined criteria

The following types of usability problems were coded:

- User (U): The problem is due to the user’s experience and knowledge.
- Hidden (H): The interface gives no indications that the function is available or how it should be used.
- Text and icon, including headings/link labels (T): Placement, appearance and content can easily be misinterpreted or misunderstood.
 - Unfamiliar text/icon: the user does not know what the label means
 - Confusable text/icon: the label could easily be confused with another label
 - Goal-specific competing text/icon: the similarity of an incorrect label to the goal is greater than the similarity of the correct label to the goal
 - Other
- Sequence (S): Functions and operations have to be performed in an unnatural sequence.
- Feedback (F): The interface gives unclear indications of what the user is doing or has done.
- Other (O)

Observed user behaviour

The following observed attitudes toward the interface were also coded (Hornbaek 2006):

- Annoyance
- Anxiety
- Complexity
- Control
- Engagement
- Flexibility
- Fun
- Intuitive
- Learnability
- Liking
- Physical discomfort
- Want to use again

Observed performance data

The following quantitative performance metrics were measured per task:

- Effectiveness: tasks completed

- Effectiveness: errors in each task
- Effectiveness: tasks with errors
- Effectiveness: task error intensity (qualitative assessment by evaluator, 1-10 scale)
- Efficiency: task time
- Efficiency: unnecessary actions (i.e., deviations from shortest path to task completion)
- Satisfaction: proportion of users complaining during the CTA

User-reported qualitative data

Respondents were asked to provide freeform answers to the following qualitative questions:

1. What was your first impression of the platform?
2. Overall, how easy or difficult was it for you to complete the tasks? Why?
3. After completing the tasks, had your first impression of the platform changed?
4. I'd like to show you a few specific pieces of content published on the platform. Please let me know whether this is something you might use in the course of your work: [SPECIFIC CONTENT ITEMS SHOWN]
5. Overall, do you think you and your colleagues would use the platform in the course of your work? Why or why not?

User-reported quantitative data

The following quantitative data, derived from the system usability scale, were collected:

- I think that I would like to use this [project] frequently.
- I found the [project] unnecessarily complex
- I thought the [project] was easy to use.
- I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this [project].
- I found the various functions in this [project] were well integrated.
- I thought there was too much inconsistency in this [project].
- I imagine that most people would learn to use this [project] very quickly.
- I found the [project] very cumbersome to use.
- I felt very confident using the [project].
- I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this [project].

The following socio-demographic data on the respondents were furthermore collected:

- Type of organisation What type of organisation do you work for?
- Level of organisation's operation (international, national, etc.)
- Sector of organisation
- Years working in current field
- Gender identity
- Age
- Highest level of education completed

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Data analysis

Approach used for the analysis of observed, measured, or collected data

During analysis, the CTA transcripts were coded using the same problem categories utilised in the CWW.

Differences in planned and collected data

No differences arose between the planned and actual data collection.

Portion of data used in the analysis

All data produced was used in the analysis.

Data scoring; data reduction; statistical analyses

The following data scoring procedures were used:

- Observed usability defects: a count was taken of all usability problems; the percentage of users encountering usability problems and percentage of tasks in which usability problems were encountered (by at least one user) were calculated
- Observed user attitudes and behaviour: the transcripts were coded and a count was taken of user attitude codes; the percentage of users who appeared to express each attitude was calculated
- Performance data based on measurements: the following were calculated:
 - Effectiveness: users completing each task
 - Effectiveness: tasks completed per user
 - Effectiveness: users encountering errors per task and in average
 - Effectiveness: errors per task and in average
 - Efficiency: time per task and in average
 - Satisfaction: percentage of users complaining during the CTA
- Problems, opinions and impressions reported by users: the qualitative exit interview transcripts were coded inductively
- Measured level of user satisfaction or perception:
 - Quantitative data derived from the system usability scale: the average SUS score, SUS score per user, and average score per SUS item were calculated
 - Sociodemographic data on the respondents: a count was taken of all sociodemographic variables

Note that the SUS scoring calculation is based on a specific framework as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\text{odd numbered questions}} - 5 &= X \\ 25 - \sum_{\text{even numbered questions}} &= Y \\ (X+Y) * 2.5 &= Z \text{ (where max } Z=100) \end{aligned}$$

6.3.2 Presentation of the results

Observed usability defects and user attitudes and behaviours

The analysis found that of 96 total tasks assigned during the testing (eight tasks assigned to each of N=12 users), 74% featured potential usability problems. The breakdown of problem types is as follows:

Table 19. Observed usability defects per problem type

Code	Problem type	Count	% of tasks assigned
NA	No usability problems	25	26%
U	The problem is due to the user's experience and knowledge.	31	32%
H	The interface gives no indications that the function is available or how it should be used.	36	38%
UT	The user does not know what the label means	14	15%
CT	The label could easily be confused with another label	33	34%
GSCT	The similarity of an incorrect label to the goal is greater than the similarity of the correct label to the goal	17	18%
OT	Other text-related problems	0	0%
S	Functions and operations have to be performed in an unnatural sequence.	41	43%
F	The interface gives unclear indications of what the user is doing or has done.	31	32%
O	Other	6	6%
Total tasks assigned	<i>Note: eight tasks assigned x N=12 users</i>	96	100%
Total tasks with any problem	<i>Note: as multiple problem types can be encountered within a single task, the column percentages for all problem types under “% of tasks assigned” add up to more than the percentage of total tasks with any problem.</i>	71	74%

The analysis furthermore found that users explicitly voiced or implicitly expressed the following negative and positive attitudes toward the platform. All users expressed some negative and some positive attitudes, but on a general level, positive expressions predominated by a significant margin.

Table 20. Observed user attitudes and behaviour

Code	No. of codes	% of users
Annoyance (negative)	3	25%
Anxiety/uncertainty (negative)	0	0%
Complexity (negative)	156	100%
Control (positive)	4	25%
Engagement (positive)	5	42%
Flexibility (positive)	1	8%
Fun (positive)	2	17%
Intuitive (positive)	312	100%
Learnability (positive)	337	100%
Liking (positive)	226	100%

Physical discomfort (negative)	6	33%
Want to use again (positive)	40	100%
Any negative expression	165	100%
Any positive expression	927	100%

For the full analysis of usability errors, see Annex 4 (T2.5_CTA_usability_errors).

Measured performance data

On average, 10 out of 12 users (83%) completed each task, with each user completing an average of 6 out of 8 tasks (80%). Across all tasks, an average of 9 out of 12 users encountered errors (74%). The average number of errors encountered per user, per task was 1,92, and the average time per task was 2 minutes and 30 seconds.

Table 21. Performance data

Task	Description	Users completing task	Users with errors	Average errors per user, per task	Average time on task
1		5 (42%)	10 (83%)	2,58	00:03:37
2		11 (92%)	7 (58%)	1,33	00:01:49
3		7 (58%)	9 (75%)	1,92	00:02:24
4		11 (92%)	6 (50%)	1,17	00:02:15
5		12 (100%)	9 (75%)	2,17	00:03:04
6		12 (100%)	11 (92%)	2,33	00:02:00
7		8 (67%)	11 (92%)	2,42	00:02:38
8		11 (92%)	8 (67%)	1,42	00:02:12
Average		10 (83%)	9 (74%)	1,92	00:02:30

For all quantitative performance data, see Annex 4 (T2.5_CTA_performance_data).

Measured level of user satisfaction

The platform received a total system usability scale score of 70, indicating good overall usability. The SUS scoring calculation is based on a specific framework as follows:

Table 1. System usability scale score

	Item	Average score (out of 5)
1	I think that I would like to use this platform frequently.	3,50
2	I found the platform unnecessarily complex	2,08
3	I thought the platform was easy to use.	3,83

4	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this platform.	1,67
5	I found the various functions in this platform were well integrated.	3,25
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this platform.	2,08
7	I imagine that most people would learn to use this platform very quickly.	3,75
8	I found the platform very cumbersome to use.	2,08
9	I felt very confident using the platform.	3,75
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this platform.	2,17
System usability scale score		70 / 100

6.3.3 Interpretation of results and recommendations

Interpretation of results

- Info boxes: not very visible, people don't find the description intuitively. This might also be due to the design of the first & third task (e.g. find out what the tab "Risk Assessment" is about and how to correctly use the tool) → Participants took two different approaches. Most people tried to figure it out by themselves and only went to the info box when stuck, while some went to the info box first before using the tool. In both cases, participants often didn't find the info box, even when asked if there were any places within the website where they could find further information.
- Maps (risk assessment & geospatial plots): Country names are written in the native language, and are not very visible, as they appear rather small and the colour contrast between the font and the colour-coded country can be quite low. This can be difficult for people that come from outside of Europe or simply lack the necessary geographic knowledge to be able to identify European countries only by their form. The question came up if the possibility to zoom in or out of the map is necessary, if only Europe is covered, and only on a country, but not a regional or municipal level.
- Sizing and appearance: Depending on the device used when looking at the website, certain parts of it might not be visible as they are blocked by other parts of the website (e.g. the "funded by the EC"- banner blocks the lower parts of most tabs within the dashboard). Scrolling is counter-intuitive, as it is only possible by mouse.
- "Risk Assessment": This tool was relatively intuitive for most participants, but people criticized that definitions and explanations were missing. Especially the aggregation function needs further information, and dimensions, results, ranks etc. need to be defined and explained. Sources need to be linked. It's not visible what data entries are mandatory to show results, some participants struggled as no map showed up, e.g., without selecting the aggregation function.
- "Geospatial Plots": Most participants were able to navigate this part of the website without difficulties, but again, explanations, definitions, and sources (or links to sources) were missing. Many disaggregation options show "N/A", which can be disturbing. Results are not explained and leave too much room for (wrong) assumptions or (mis)interpretation. → Because of this, some users thought that the results could be considered unreliable!

- “Indicator Comparison”: The tasks within the “indicator comparison”- tab were slightly more difficult to complete, as people first tried to compare values within the tab “geospatial plots”, which is due to the task sequence, not the website; once the right tab was found, completion was easy. Again, definitions, links to sources and explanations of results are needed, and the overkill in disaggregation options showing “N/A” are distracting and give an unreliable image. The scatterplot was not very appealing to most participants, legends are missing, and it is not self-explanatory that you need to hover your mouse over the dots to see the data. Participants also didn’t like the “download chart”-option, as the html-download is not practical. For many, the reason to download a cart is because they want to use the chart in a presentation or report, and thus need a jpg, or png format or similar. These images also need to contain a legend and the data source.
- “COVID-19 Trends”: Just as with the indicator comparison, the task sequence and goal definition led to most errors. Most people first stayed in the tab “indicator comparison” when asked to compare “vaccination rates” and “excess deaths” between France and Spain; Once they saw that these indicators were not available within the tab, they quickly moved to “COVID-19 Trends”, and had little to no issues within this tab. This part of the website, as well as the graphs available, was highly appreciated and participants indicated that they would use this tool in their work. However, definitions and links to sources, as well as more recent data would be appreciated. Finally, the possibility to download the data as a spreadsheet would also be a big plus.
- “Case Studies”: Quite a large number of errors was revealed within this tab. Case studies were visible for two locations only, Wales and Greece. Even if Portugal could be selected, no text showed up. For Greece, the SES-Framework and the lessons learned did not change and still show those from Wales. The links to the full report were missing for all countries. People struggled to find the quotes behind the clickable speech bubbles, as nothing indicated that the image is interactive, which is why the failure rate is rather high for this task (4 out of 12, 33%). When the quotes were found, most participants were positively surprised and liked the idea, but criticized that there needs to be some sort of indication or explanation, and they would also like to have the source of the quotes.
- “Knowledge Repository”: This tab was easy to find, and most participants were able to use this tool intuitively. A couple of issues occurred. First, when typing in a keyword and no results appeared, people were confused and thought that the website was still charging. Second, searching by name/author/keyword was not always understood or considered necessary. Third, certain output types showed up twice in the drop-down menu, e.g., “Report” and “Reports, or “Brief” and “Briefs”. Finally, multiple publications led to a google drive, where access needed to be requested, which would have been a “red flag” for most participants. It was perceived as unprofessional and untrustworthy.

Recommendations

- Info boxes: Make the explanations more visible, either by integrating the text directly into the page, e.g., on top of the tool, by moving the info-box icon to the left, by showing explanations to the different options when hovering over them, or by placing info boxes right next to the options → This is relevant for all tabs.

- Definitions: Add definitions to indicators, data sets, results, dimensions (Risk assessment), etc. to make them more comprehensible. If Eurostat data is used, check if they offer official definitions (likely). → This is relevant for all tabs.
- Explanations: Add minimal explanations to more complex parts of the website, such as the aggregation function within the risk assessment tab (see the point about info boxes). This could either be in the form of written explanations, or by including links to trustworthy explanations. It would be beneficial to include the explanation right next to the item concerned, e.g., a selection button or graph, so that it is immediately visible. This could either be done by adding a clickable icon next to the point in question, or that text appears once you hover over it with your mouse. Consider adding a minimum of explanation to the results, especially those of the risk assessment, to put it into context and make it more understandable. → This is relevant for all tabs.
- Sources: Sources should be visible in all results (they mostly are). Adding links to the data source, e.g., Eurostat would be beneficial. Also consider adding an option to download the data as an excel sheet. → This is relevant for all tabs.
- Disaggregation options: Reduce the disaggregation option to only those available, e.g., if a data set only has two levels of disaggregation, make sure that only two drop-down-menus appear. The “N/A”s give an unprofessional image and cause confusion. → This is relevant for geospatial plots & indicator comparison.
- Maps: Write country names in English, increase the font size, and make sure the font colour is visible. Consider whether the possibility to zoom in and out of the map, or move the map, is necessary. → Relevant for Risk assessment & Geospatial plots.
- Appearance: Make sure the website is visible on different screen sizes and that no parts of the website are blocked by other parts. (e.g., maybe the “funded by the EC” banner doesn’t need to be visible at all times, but only when scrolling down) → This is relevant for all tabs.
- Risk assessment: Clarify, which data needs to be selected for the tool to work, e.g., by adding asterixis. Consider starting with pre-set data to show a map from the beginning and thereby avoid confusion.
- Geospatial plots: Make sure the graphs within the map are not blocked by other parts of the website.
- Indicator comparison: rethink the scatterplot. Add legends, increase the dots, make sure the description of the x-axis is not blocked by the “Funded by the EC”-banner. Add the possibility to download as a jpg or png, that can be used for presentations or reports. Make sure that the downloadable chart is readable without the html-functions.
- COVID-19 Trends: add more recent data if available! This concerns all tabs but is especially relevant for COVID-19 related data.
- Case Studies: add all case study locations, make sure the SES framework, lessons learned, and quotes match the location selected; add links to the full reports; better indicate that the speech bubbles are clickable, by adding text into the speech bubbles, e.g., “Community is...”, “Resilience is...” etc., by adding a little “Click me!” icon to the picture, and/or by animating the picture, so that the speech bubbles increase and decrease a couple of times when first opening the tab. Add sources to the quotations: Profession, gender, age, location! Also mention in the source that the quotations stem from our own research.
- Knowledge repository: Reconsider the “search by” option, maybe keywords are enough. Merge the duplications in the document-type drop-down menu. Clarify when no results can

be found, e.g. by adding the phrase “No results available”, and consider adding a “search” button to start searching. Make sure all publications are accessible!

7 Ethical considerations

Only anonymous data has been collected. While no personal data has been collected, a project information sheet and GDPR-compliant (digital or paper) informed consent document was presented asking participants to consent to participate in the usability test.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable summarises the findings of the COVINFORM risk assessment dashboard usability testing sequence, which entailed three workshops and a round of individual usability tests.

As stated in the Executive Summary, the workshops, conducted with project partners, found a number of minor issues but generally suggested good usability. The individual usability tests, conducted with external end-users, identified several more basic challenges. This differential was expected based on the difference in contextual knowledge between the internal workshop participants and the external end-users. The end-user feedback will prove critical in the finalisation of the dashboard, as well as in planning its future exploitation.

A changelog with indications of which recommendations were implemented by October 2023 is provided in COVINFORM D2.9, “Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers”.

Annex I: Workshop 1 questionnaire and agenda

User requirements questionnaire

COVINFORM Partner Questionnaire – User Requirements [WP2]

Purpose: The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather the COVINFORM partners initial user requirements for the interactive, geospatial cloud-based risk assessment model built in WP2 with end-user involvement (Task 2.5).

Aim: To identify and assess relevant datasets, indicators and models that will inform the development of risk assessment tools to map the impact of governmental responses to COVID-19, with a specific focus on vulnerable groups.

Methods: To understand the needs of project partners, ‘User Stories’ will be obtained from each participating project partner. User stories are used to capture (and discover) the desired product functionality and its value from the user’s perspective. The value of employing user stories is that they compel both the developer and the end user to focus on understanding the *why* part of the user requirement.

Participants: All COVINFORM project partners will be asked to submit their ‘User Stories’ prior to the first User Requirement Workshop. To gain the most valuable insights, we would ask that more than one participant per partner organisation completes the questionnaire. Ideally, multiple partner roles and fields of work will be represented in the final responses.

User Stories (Pre-workshop User Stories)

Thank you for taking the time to consider our questionnaire. We hope to gain some insights from your experience in accessing data and information during the pandemic.

Please complete all questions.

My role is _____ and involves:

1. In my role, I want to [conduct/respond/identify/gain insight]:

in [geographical area level]:

so I can achieve [outcome]:
2. “During the pandemic, within my role, I typically sought data/information regarding vulnerable groups from (e.g., websites, groups, institutions, individuals)
(include a list of resources including publicly available and institutional datasets):
3. And what was this data/information used for?
4. I was usually [satisfied/dissatisfied] with the data/information available.
5. In cases in which I was mostly satisfied, it was due to the data/information or data sources being (please list all positive attributes):
6. In cases in which I was mostly dissatisfied, it was due to the data/information or data sources being (please list all negative attributes):
7. Can you describe the last time you sought data on vulnerable groups and detail the process that you followed?
8. What level of technical knowledge or experience was required for you to interpret the data/knowledge to make decisions?
9. What barriers or challenges did you face in identifying at-risk groups, and finding implementable and trusted actions, which achieved meaningful impacts?

10. My organisation currently defines 'at-risk' as [characteristics/s]:

but this doesn't account for [characteristic/s]:

11. Is your organisation's definition of 'at-risk' formal/explicit or informal/implicit?

Thank you for completing the questionnaire.

Please send your completed questionnaire to the WP2 Leader at Trilateral Research (Niamh Aspell; Niamh.aspell@trilateralresearch.com and Su Anson Susan.anson@trilateralresearch.com).

All responses will be reviewed, and a summary of findings will be discussed during the first User Requirement Workshop (date to be confirmed).

User requirements workshop agenda

- Introductions and participant roles
- Presentation: WP2 Overview [TRI]
- Presentation: Overview of data identified and data sources [TRI: Technical Team]
- Presentation: Overview of relevant indicators and composite indicators [TRI]
- Review of partner User Requirement Stories (Appendix 1: User Requirements Questionnaire)
- Pilot of platform [TRI Technical Team]
- Breakout groups (4 participants from a range of stakeholders i.e., responders, researchers)
- Breakout groups presentations
- Discussion

The aim of the focus groups will be to identify “must-have” and “desirable” requirements of the platform. Breakout groups will take the form of a co-creation workshop and will mock design the functionalities of the interface (Minimal Fakeable Product).

Each focus group will have a nominated presenter to deliver an overview of the requirements identified in their group discussions.

To generate discussion focus groups should discuss the following.

1. 'As a [user role], I want to [conduct/respond/identify/gain insight], in [geographical area level], during [X] phase of the COVID-19, so I can achieve [outcome]'
2. 'What data do you wish you had access to _____?'
3. 'If I have indicator data to show [risk], I can respond by [action] to achieve [outcome]'
4. "The ideal risk assessment model would provide me with information on [situation/needs/population/proposed actions]"
5. "I envisage using the interactive software for [task], so I would need [requirements] in order for me to determine [outcome]".

Annex II: Workshop 2 & 3 protocol

The cognitive walkthrough agenda is as follows.

Table. CWW Agenda

Time	Phase	Phase name
T	A	Confirm target user groups
T+10	A	Confirm assumptions about target users
T+20	A	Confirm user knowledge requirements
T+30	B	Define user tasks
T+60	C	Identification of user-task-specific problems
T+90	End	Conclusion

A. Target users / personas

i. Target user groups

The participants should review the target user groups identified in the Description of Action and discuss whether they have remained constant, drawing on the work done in the project to date (i.e., desk research in WP2 and empirical research in WP3).

ii. Assumptions about target users

The participants should discuss what attributes are likely to characterise the target users, drawing on the work done in the project to date (i.e., desk research in WP2 and empirical research in WP3).

iii. User knowledge requirements

The participants should discuss what knowledge and competences the users can be expected to have, and cross-reference this with the types of knowledge and competence required to use the platform.

B. User tasks and intended selections

Based on the conclusions reached in the prior section, the participants should identify between one and ten tasks representative of those performed by potential users in the course of their work. For each task, a correct use flow should be identified. An example follows:

User task 1

3. Goal description

Example: Access a COVINFORM Project Insights document relevant to your field of practice.

4. Correct use flow

Example: Select "Knowledge" → select "Project Insights" → look through the documents and identify one that is relevant

C. Credible success stories per task

The participants should walk through each task step-by-step, asking and discussing the five questions required to establish a “credible success story” (as inspired by Wharton et al. 1993 and Blackmon et al. 2002):

1. Will the correct use flow be clear to the user?
2. Will the user connect the correct action description with what he or she is trying to do?
3. Will the user navigate to the correct subregion of the page, using heading information and her understanding of the site’s layout?
4. Will the user utilise the correct widgets in the relevant subregion of the page, using link labels and other kinds of descriptive information?
5. Will the user interpret the system’s response to the chosen action correctly?

During the discussion, the moderator should take notes. An example based on Task 1 above follows:

User task 1: Find out what the tab “Risk Assessment” is about and how to correctly use the tool.

5. Will the correct use flow be clear the user?

The correct use flow is: select “Risk Assessment” → click on the information button. The use flow should be clear; however, the information button may not be immediately visible.

6. Will the user connect the correct action descriptions with what she is trying to do?

Yes. The labels are clear.

7. Will the user navigate to the correct subregion of the page, using heading information and her understanding of the site’s layout?

Possibly. The labels are clear, but the information button may not be immediately visible.

8. Will the user utilise the correct widgets in the relevant subregion of the page, using link labels and other kinds of descriptive information?

Yes. Clicking the button is intuitive.

9. Will the user correctly interpret the system’s response (feedback) to the chosen action?

Yes. All links and widgets work.

D. Concluding discussion

The participants should take a step back, discussing how any potential problems identified during the semantic analysis and/or the walkthrough of credible success stories might impact the usability of the page as a whole. The participants should conclude by brainstorming a set of potential recommendations for the developers.

Annex III: Concurrent think-aloud test protocol

a. Description of the protocol

Think-aloud methods are a well-established method of studying “task-based cognitive processes” in general, and human-computer interactions in particular (McDonald et al. 2012, pg. 3).

In the “classic” concurrent think-aloud (CTA) method, based on Ericsson and Simon’s work (1993), a single user undertakes a set of target tasks, while an evaluator observes and records them. Ericsson and Simon recommend taking standardised measures to maximise the utility and neutrality of the narrative data elicited: these include offering warm-up / practice opportunities; keeping written scripts as neutral as possible; keeping evaluator probes as general as possible (e.g., “keep talking”); and generally minimising interaction between the evaluator and the user.

The protocol begins with a warm-up during which the think-aloud concept is concisely explained and the participant is given the chance to practice thinking aloud while completing a simple task (e.g., searching for a credible information source on Google). The participant is then given a selection of written scripts describing tasks to perform on the COVINFORM website. The scripts are kept as neutral as possible. During the test itself, the evaluators are instructed to minimise their interaction with the participants, whenever possible restricting their probes to Ericsson and Simon’s Level 1 and 2 prompts and restrained “acknowledgement tokens”. Level 3 prompts are only used if absolutely necessary to the successful completion of the test.

- Levels 1 and 2: reminders to “keep talking” and acknowledgement tokens (e.g., “um-hmm”)
- Level 3: questions about specific actions or the thoughts behind them (e.g., “why did you click on that purple tab?”)

The test protocol is designed to take ca. 20-25 minutes. The participants are also asked to conduct a ca. 5-10 minute exit interview, for a total length-of-interview of ca. 30 to maximum 40 minutes. The exit interview begins with a few open questions about overall usability, and ends with the administration of the system usability scale (SUS) questionnaire, which consists of nine general usability questions scored using a five-point Likert-type scale, as well as a socio-demographic questionnaire. After completing these questionnaires, the participants are given the option of sharing their SUS scores with the evaluator and explaining why they scored particular SUS items the way that they did; however, this is not mandatory.

The test will be conducted online using screen-sharing, and will be video recorded.

During analysis by SINUS, the CTA transcripts will be coded using the same problem categories utilised in the CWW:

- User (U): The problem is due to the user’s experience and knowledge.
- Hidden (H): The interface gives no indications that the function is available or how it should be used.
- Text and icon, including headings/link labels (T): Placement, appearance and content can easily be misinterpreted or misunderstood.
 - Unfamiliar text/icon: the user does not know what the label means
 - Confusable text/icon: the label could easily be confused with another label

- Goal-specific competing text/icon: the similarity of an incorrect label to the goal is greater than the similarity of the correct label to the goal
- Other
- Sequence (S): Functions and operations have to be performed in an unnatural sequence.
- Feedback (F): The interface gives unclear indications of what the user is doing or has done.
- Other (O)

The following codes identifying specific attitudes toward the interface will also be used in the transcript analysis (Hornbaek 2006):

- Annoyance
- Anxiety
- Complexity
- Control
- Engagement
- Flexibility
- Fun
- Intuitive
- Learnability
- Liking
- Physical discomfort
- Want to use again

Finally, the following quantitative performance metrics will be measured per task:

- Effectiveness: tasks completed
- Effectiveness: errors in each task
- Effectiveness: tasks with errors
- Effectiveness: task error intensity (qualitative assessment by evaluator, 1-10 scale)
- Efficiency: task time
- Efficiency: unnecessary actions (i.e., deviations from shortest path to task completion)
- Satisfaction: proportion of users complaining during the CTA

b. Warm-up task

Interviewer: this test will use a method called “think-aloud”, in which you complete a few tasks while narrating what you are doing and thinking. I’ll show you an example of how this is done, and then ask you to try it yourself. As an example, I’ll give myself the task of finding the current COVID-19 case rate in Germany. Now I will start the task while thinking aloud.

I’m opening my web browser and navigating to google.com, the search engine I usually use. Now I’m searching “COVID case rates Germany”. Here I see a chart: it’s called “Statistics – New cases and deaths – From JHU CSSE COVID-19 Data – Last updated: 6 hours ago”. JHU means Jons Hopkins University, that sounds like a credible source. I’ve completed the task.

Do you have any questions about the think-aloud procedure that I just demonstrated?

Now I’d like you to try: please find the number of people who claimed asylum in Germany in 2021.

c. User tasks

Interviewer instruction: ask the user to share their screen, open their web browser, and navigate to <https://covinform.striad.trilateral.ai/homepage>.

Interviewer: We will take a look at the Covinform Dashboard today and perform a couple of simple tasks. Before we start the tasks, what is your very first impression of the dashboard?

Interviewer instruction: ask the user to complete each task. DO NOT describe the proper use flow – allow the user to figure it out. While the user is completing the task, try to speak as little as possible – however, if the user forgets to keep speaking aloud, remind them.

If the user appears to have completed a task, confirm verbally that the task is complete and move to the next. If the user cannot complete a task, wait until the user has reached a point of frustration and then ask if the user would like to move on.

https://covinform.striad.trilateral.ai/homepage		
Task	Description	Scenario (use flow)
1	Find out what the tab “Risk Assessment” is about and how to correctly use the tool.	Select “Risk Assessment” → click on the information button
2	Find out the Risk assessment for Sweden in a domain that is relevant to your field and find the country’s rank.	Select “Risk Assessment” → select Year and Aggregation function → select domain → select country “Sweden” → read “Rank”
3	Find out what the tab “Geospatial Plots” is about and how to correctly use the tool.	Select “Geospatial Plots” → click on the information button
4	Find the digital access rate for households in rural areas in Italy, as of 2019	Select “Geospatial Plots” → select data set → select household type → select year → click on Italy and read the number
5	Compare the government health spending and vaccine affordability and download the chart. Make sure you have all relevant information to use the tool.	Select “Indicator Comparisons” → click on the information button → Select first data set “Government Health Spending” → Select second data set “Vaccine Affordability” → Click on “Download Chart”
6	Compare the developments of Vaccination Rates and Number of Excess Deaths between France and Spain. Make sure you have all relevant information to use the tool.	Select “Covid-19 Trends” → click on the information button → Select first data set “Covid-19 Vaccination Rates” → Select second data set “Excess Deaths!” → Select Country → Click on “Compare Trends from Two Countries” → Select second country
7	Find the case study about Greece and find a quote about community. Make sure you have all relevant information to navigate the website.	Select “Case Study” → click on the information button → Select “Greece” → Scroll down to lessons learnt → click on the speech bubble saying “Community is...”
8	Find a COVINFORM output relevant to your field of interest. Make sure you have all relevant information to navigate the website.	Select “Knowledge Repositors” → click on the information button → Select document type “Covinform Output” → select topic of interest → select initiative

d. Exit interview

Interviewer instruction: inform the user that we will end the test with a few open questions, followed by a short questionnaire.

Interviewer: thank you for completing the tasks! We'd like to ask a couple of follow-up questions.

1. After using the platform for a while, what was your impression of it in general?
2. Overall, how easy or difficult was it to complete the tasks? Why?
3. After completing the tasks, had your impression of the platform changed?
4. Compared to current platforms on the internet: does the platform offer anything new and valuable, or does it mostly duplicate what is already out there?
5. Overall, do you think you and your colleagues would use the platform and its content in the course of your work? Why or why not?

Interviewer: finally, we'll go through two quick questionnaires together.

e. System usability scale questionnaire

System usability scale

	Item	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
1	I think that I would like to use this [project] frequently.					
2	I found the [project] unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the [project] was easy to use.					
4	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this [project].					
5	I found the various functions in this [project] were well integrated.					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this [project].					
7	I imagine that most people would learn to use this [project] very quickly.					
8	I found the [project] very cumbersome to use.					
9	I felt very confident using the [project].					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this [project].					

The SUS scoring calculation is based on a specific framework as follows:

- a. $\sum_{\text{odd numbered questions}} - 5 = X$
- b. $\sum_{\text{even numbered questions}} - 5 = Y$

c. $(X+Y) * 2.5 = Z$ (where max Z=100)

f. Socio-demographic questionnaire

1. What type of organisation do you work for?
 - a. Governmental (public organisations working in one country)
 - b. Intergovernmental (public organisations working across more than one country e.g. EU organisations)
 - c. Non-governmental (faith-based)
 - d. Non-governmental (non-faith based)
 - e. Private company
 - f. Freelancer
 - g. Other (please specify in the next question)
2. On what level does your organisation mostly work?
 - a. International
 - b. Federal/national
 - c. State/prefectural
 - d. Local/communal
3. In what sector does your organisation primarily operate?
 - a. Public health
 - b. Social services
 - c. Education
 - d. Research
 - e. Crisis management
 - f. Other:
4. About how many years have you been working in your current field?
 - a. 1-5 years or less
 - b. 6-10 years
 - c. More than 10 years
5. What is your gender identity?
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Other
 - d. Choose not to answer
6. How old are you?
 - a. 18-19
 - b. 20-29
 - c. 30-39
 - d. 40-49
 - e. 50-59
 - f. 60-69
 - g. 70 or above
 - h. Choose not to answer
7. What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 - a. Primary education
 - b. Secondary education

- c. Vocational training or professional certificate
- d. Bachelor's degree
- e. Master's degree
- f. Doctorate

Annex IV: Test data

Please see the test data spreadsheets in the file COVINFORM_D2.5_Annex_4.zip, downloadable via this secure link: <https://cloud.sinus-institut.de/public/740b0f>

References

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Websites

<https://covinform.striad.trilateral.ai/home>